

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL ACTIONS OF YOUNG GOALKEEPERS

BAXTIYOROV D.B

TEACHER OF THE UZBEK STATE UNIVERSITY OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND
SPORTS.

ODILOV R.F

TEACHER OF THE UZBEK STATE UNIVERSITY OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND
SPORTS.

BURKHONOV B.KH

TRAINING INSTITUTE OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN THE TEACHER OF THE "PHYSICAL TRAINING" CYCLE
IS LEITINANT

JO'RABOYEV M.T

TRAINING INSTITUTE OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN THE TEACHER OF THE "PHYSICAL TRAINING" CYCLE
IS LEITINANT

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Abstract. *The article focuses on the reliability and effectiveness of technical methods and development of tactical actions by young and qualified goalkeepers in the training of amputee football players.*

Keywords: *Pacification, Internet, pulsometry, anthropometry, troectory, element, technique, tactics, training.*

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ТЕХНИКО-ТАКТИЧЕСКИХ ДЕЙСТВИЙ ЮНЫХ ВРАТАРЕЙ

Аннотация. *В статье акцентируется внимание на надежности и эффективности технических приемов и отработки тактических действий молодыми и квалифицированными вратарями при подготовке футболистов-ампутантов.*

Ключевые слова: *Умиротворение, Интернет, пульсометрия, антропометрия, троектория, элемент, техника, тактика, тренировка.*

Relevance: In our country, a number of activities aimed at taking care of young people and helping them find their place in social life are being carried out. In particular, serious attention is being paid to the issues of improving the education system, bringing up the generation that will contribute to the development of the Motherland. As in other sports, improving sports skills in football requires the foundation of the sports training system of all line players, especially the goalkeeper. It requires the goalkeeper not only to be able to defend the goal with skill, but also to be active in the penalty area, as well as to be able to lead all the defenders. The goalkeeper coordinates all defensive actions of the team. The fact that the goalkeeper is behind everyone helps him to see the positions of the attackers, their intentions (which the defenders may not understand). In addition, the goalkeeper is the player who initiates most of the team's attacks, and as a result, it is mostly up to the goalkeeper to maintain the initiative and organize attacks. Taking into account the above, there is a need to develop the goalkeeper's technical and tactical actions on the field, and this situation determines the relevance of this study.

The purpose of the study. The goal is to develop recommendations for determining the effectiveness and reliability of technical-tactical actions (TTX) of young and qualified goalkeepers.

Research tasks.

Developing a method of monitoring and evaluating technical and tactical training indicators of young and qualified goalkeepers in competition and training conditions;

Determine the numerical characteristics of the actions performed by the goalkeepers in training and compare them with their performance in the game;

Determining the effectiveness and reliability of goalkeepers' actions in training competition conditions.

Research methods. Research and analysis of scientific and methodological literature, pedagogical observation, pedagogical control, pedagogical testing, pulsometry, anthropometry, analysis of the training process, pedagogical experience, mathematical and statistical methods were used.

Organization of research. Tashkent city Yashnobot district Aviasozlar 1 daha 82 A house Taoshkent city children and youth football academy training process.

Research results and its discussion. The goalkeeper's ability to choose the right place (position) also allows the goalkeeper to reliably receive balls aimed at the goal with minimal effort. A goalkeeper who chooses his position well rarely falls on the ball. This gives the impression that the striker is chasing the goalkeeper and directing the ball. That is why the ability to choose a position is given the highest value. [91,81,71,61,51,41,31,21,11,1.]

Currently, it is impossible to imagine a goalkeeper who does not manage the organization of the attack and especially the defense of the whole team. The goalkeeper quickly assesses the game situation and knows the direction of the attack. In order to generalize the experience, interviews were held between the trainers of the teams and the trainers who work with the young players during training sessions with young and qualified amputee goalkeepers. [92,82,72,62,52,42,32,22,12,2.] A total of 24 people passed the survey. During the interviews with the trainers, we tried to determine the specific features and directions of working with the goalkeepers. The reliability and effectiveness of technical methods by qualified and young goalkeepers have been determined during training and competitions. [93,83,73,63,53,43,33,23,13,3.] During the training, technical methods were improved according to age levels. In this, the techniques of catching the ball, hitting the ball, jumping the ball to another place were developed, and reliability and efficiency indicators were determined (see Table 1).

I- Table.

Technical methods	Goalkeepers			
	Qualified		Young	
	Reliability	Efficiency	Reliability	Efficiency
Jump and fall without jumping to catch the ball	0,64	19,5	0,61	13,2
	0,67	11,1	12,1 0,77	13,4 10,3
	0,67	5,6	0,48	4,2
Hit the ball by jumping and falling without jumping	0,75	8,4	0,50	4,2
	0,67	5,6	6,5 0,65	8,4 5,7
	0,67	5,5	0,49	4,4
Pass the ball to another place by jumping into the corner	-	-	-	-
	0,67	5,5	0,67	8,9

	0,66	5,5	5,5 0,51	4,4 6,6
Average	0,68		8,0 0,59	7,5
Total:		66,7		6,1

This, in turn, requires special attention to be paid to the improvement of these movement methods during the training process. By comparing the indicators representing the movements observed in the game during the previous performance of the goalkeepers, it can be said that there are differences in the reliability of the performance of the movements, although there are significant differences in quality. These differences are especially noticeable when catching the ball without jumping and hitting the ball while falling. [84,74,64,54,44,34,24,14,4.]

The situation at the bottom is very bad, the goalkeepers are more reliable when they play forward, using jumps and falls. For older skilled goalkeepers, the most reliable method is to hit the ball, and for young goalkeepers, the most reliable method is to jump and catch the ball. When considering the methods of attack, it is necessary to emphasize the importance of the goalkeeper in these situations, in order to continue the attack later, it is very important for him to direct the ball to whom and how accurately and rationally. [85,75,65,55,45,35,25,15,5] From the observations, it was found that goalkeepers often use different methods of hitting the ball to organize offensive actions. Throwing the ball into play from the goal is considered the least effective method of putting the ball into play for highly skilled goalkeepers. Throwing the ball by hand is considered the most effective and reliable way for goalkeepers to start an attack. In the table you can see different kicks performed by goalkeepers. However, it should be noted that these kicks of the goalkeepers are not always accurately performed, and one out of two such kicks is passed inaccurately. [86,76,66,56,46,36,26,16,] The reasons for this are as follows: pauses in hitting the ball (if it is not intended from a tactical point of view), an unexpected situation when putting the ball into play, the absence of an element, after the ball was hit, it flew up for a long time. All this allows them to compete with them one-on-one or surpass them. At the same time, if the goalkeeper is able to bring the ball into the game unexpectedly and quickly, the technical-tactical action will be highly effective. Based on pedagogical observations, such a method does not justify itself in organizing an attack at home. Techniques involving jumping and falling to hit the ball are less effective. Techniques associated with falling and jumping to catch the ball in forward play are both less effective and less reliable. [87,77,67,57,47,37,27,17,7.] This can be explained by the fact that when the ball is raised in the penalty area, a large number of players gather in this direction. In such a situation, the goalkeeper can't always get the right shot, he can make a mistake, that is, he can get to the ball late or early, causing a dangerous situation.

Table II

Results of goalkeepers' technical actions (p = 4 g)

Technical methods	Goalkeepers	
	experimental group	control group

Catch the ball				
Without jumping	21	90%	15	88%
Jump	12	82%	14	91%
Fell down	16	72%	19	81%
Return the ball				
Without jumping	18	69%	24	72%
Falling down	23	55%	26	61%
Hit the ball				
Behind the gate	15	85%	11	92%
Jump forward	25	78%	21	80%

Pedagogical observation was carried out in our work. Pedagogical observation was observed in the football season of 2022 in the teams of the first league. The technical and tactical actions of the goalkeepers of the Matonat and Internalminal teams were analyzed in the 2nd round of the Uzbekistan Championship among amputees in football. The results of the game shown by the goalkeepers on the fields are high, and the Internet was also used in its analysis. [88,78,68,58,48,38,28,18,8.]

During the second round, more than 15 games were observed and analyzed. Observations have shown that the duties of a goalkeeper in football consist of three main tasks: playing in the goal, actions during throws and organizing the attack. Goalkeepers need to be highly refined in technical hand movements, that is, catching the ball and returning the ball. In the matches, the goalkeepers showed the following confident results in manual technical movements. They were 96% effective in intercepting balls rolling towards the goal at an average speed, 92% in catching the ball from above and below, 55% in rebounding, and 33% in rebounding from the floor. Correctly selected position is also of great importance in eliminating shots given to goalkeepers. Catching the ball in corner kicks or kicking the ball requires great skill of the goalkeeper. The goals scored from the corner (next) in the matches are mainly due to the goalkeeper's defenses, i.e., jumping to the ball, technical error from catching the ball, kick from the corner, failure to take into account the trajectory of the ball in flight. The goalkeeper's lack of good position and understanding with the defenders was duly punished by the opponent's attackers. The main reason for this is that the defender trusts the goalkeeper in most cases. When we watched the games, such situations were repeated many times in the meeting between strong and weak teams, the weak team scored more balls into the strong team's goal. On the one hand, this game confirms the importance of accurate placement of techniques for successful possession, and on the other hand, it shows the lack of preparation of goalkeepers to act in situations when techniques have to be used when jumping and falling. In the course of our research, as a result of using the goalkeeper's technical-tactical methods in training, he took an honorable place in the championship of Uzbekistan. [89,79,69,59,49,39,29,19,90]

In short, by using methods of improving the goalkeeper's technical and tactical movements on the field, the possibilities of protecting the goal of the national team of Uzbekistan at the World Asian Championships have been expanded, by skillfully protecting the goal and achieving good results in domestic competitions depending on the effectiveness of the actions.

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